

ANNUAL MANDATORY MONEY TARIFF CHANGE IN BATAM: POLITICAL ECONOMY REVIEW

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Abstract

Annual mandatory money is land lease cost that must be paid by user of land allocation in Batam Island to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). BIFZA changes annual mandatory money tariff through BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016. It makes problems that are [1] Rejection of community elements; [2] Sluggishness of economic growth; [3] Incoordination with outside stakeholders; and [4] Disadvantage threat to workers. This research objectives, first, identify and explain reason of annual mandatory money tariff change. Second, it identifies and explains advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change. This research uses rational choice theory and public choice theory which are from new political economy school as a theoretical frameworks. Approach is used by qualitative with descriptive analysis methods. Data is collected by interview and documentation study. Data was collected for it is analyzed by process of reduction, presentation, and verification. Research result concluded that, first, reason of annual mandatory money tariff change is caused by unilateral action from BIFZA that changes it by outside stakeholders incoordination. Second, advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change show that advantage side is BIFZA and foreign investor. While, disadvantage side is community, businessman, and worker.

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1. Introduction

Annual mandatory money is land lease cost that must be paid by user of land allocation in Batam Island who is characterized by individual, investor, or legal entity to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). Income of annual mandatory money is used by BIFZA as development of in infrastructure and public facilities so Batam can be said a city of very rapid in business climate growth city in Indonesia [1]. Annual mandatory money payment is paid every 30 years for the first time, and it is next every 20 years forever. All of land in Batam Island can only be leased through annual mandatory money tariff because the land is owned by the state. The authority for land management rights had been given by Central Government to Batam Island Industrial Area Development Authority which based at Presidential Decree Number 41 of 1973 and it has delegated to BIFZA (new name from Batam Island Industrial Area Development Authority) which based at Government Regulation Number 46 of 2007 [2 p23]. The status of land in Batam Island can only be in the form of business rights, building rights, and used rights which based at Government Regulation Number 40 of 1996.

BIFZA changes annual mandatory money tariff that based at BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016. The comparison between old and new annual mandatory money tariff is increased from range of 151,7% to 2640,4% to all allocations that are housing, commercial, industrial, tourism, cultivation area, and public facilities. It makes problems that are *first*, rejection of community elements. The rejection was carried out by *Melayu Melawan* at 2 November 2016 [3], businessmen at 2 November 2016 [4], workers at 9-10 November 2016 [5], *Gerakan Rakyat Melawan UWTO* at 14-16 November 2016 [6], Regional House of Representatives of Batam City

at 14 October 2016 [7], and Batam City Government at 25 October 2016 [8]. *Second*, sluggishness of economic growth. Batam's economic growth in 2016 numbered to 5.45% is slowing that compared to growth in 2015 that numbered to 6.83% [9 p55]. *Third*, incoordination with outside stakeholders. A member of the Batam Area Council, Jumaga Nadeak admitted that he refused annual mandatory money tariff change [10] because other than businessmen disadvantage and the discussion did not involve Batam Area Council. *Fourth*, disadvantage threat to workers. Chair of All Indonesian Workers Union of Kepulauan Riau Province, Syaiful Badri said that annual mandatory money tariff change would add burden to workers because the workers and investment world could not be separated [5].

1. 1. Objective

Based on the research question identified earlier, so objectives, first, identify and explain reason of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Second, it identifies and explains advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016.

2. Theoretical Framework

Political economy is understood to analyze political processes in relation with economy or it is the systematic study of about the relationship between economic process and political process [11]. This research uses rational choice theory and public choice theory which are from new political economy school as a theoretical frameworks.

2. 1. Rational Choice Theory

According to Deliarnov [12 p134] in general, rationality developed by new political economy experts, especially in rational choices, is related to concepts such as preference, beliefs, opportunities, and action. To be more easily understood, example we are faced by two choices, namely A and B. Three ways to express preferences between the two choices are (1) A is better than B (notated with $A > B$); (2) B is better than A (notated with $B > A$ or $A < B$); and (3) A is as good as (or as bad as) B (notated with $A=B$). If you were ranking $A > B$ and $B > C$, based on theory of revealed preference and according to transitivity axiom, the conclusions are $A > C$. The concept of rational choice can be applied to the government as an actor or to individual voters in elections because the criteria used are same, and opportunities considered comparable. For new political economy experts, the important is that rational choices can be carried out, either by individuals or by the government. They do not reject the framework of political existence, but they assume that political behavior and political institutions can be analyzed as well as economic behavior and market institutions.

2. 2. Public Choice Theory

James Buchanan [13 p70] reviewed it from two separate aspects which are two main elements from a public choice perspective. The first aspect is the exchange aspect (*catallactics*). If you use *catallactics* in more deeply, then this perspective can succeed in bringing the definition of spontaneous and complex order into a simple concept of exchange. This complex exchange is a process of contractual agreement that can be given more meaning than just the exchange of two people who make transactions. If economics can explain market phenomena, namely meetings between seller and buyer, then new political economy can also explain the concept of political markets. Market in the economics are governed by basic laws, namely spontaneous order. Meanwhile, the political market is used as a concept to explain the exchange between political parties and voters and between the government in power and people. The foundation of the political market is the game rules of constitutional and democratic, not on the basis of power.

While, the second aspect is a postulation, known as economical human (*homo economicus*). It is used to explain the inclusive public choice perspective. The true meaning of this concept is that humans tend to maximize utility benefits for themselves because they are faced

with the reality of limited resources their have. Everyone experiences a problem of scarcity of resources so the concept of *homo economicus* automatically explains the consequences of human behavior on the action or economic satisfaction that it does. All people will have the tendency of *homo economicus*. So, this concept has nothing to do with the nature of capitalism, greed or economical animal. Technically, this concept is described in the utility function where individual continues to strive that fulfills his/her self interest. This nature means very basic so no one individual is free from it (except the abnormal). Self interest is a very human nature that cannot be revoked or arbitrarily restricted by anyone. From this intrinsic meaning, collective model can be built without losing human nature.

3. Method

Approach is used by qualitative with descriptive analysis methods. Qualitative is the emphasis on processes and meanings that are not tested, or measured precisely, in terms of quantity, number, intent, or frequency [14 p14]. This approach try to understand information in description form of phenomena between supplier and demander in responded about problems of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. For obtaining primary data sources, researcher uses purposive technique to determine informants. By purposive technique, informants were deliberately chosen with certain considerations [15 p318] that are knowing, competent, and involved with the research topic. The informants are Head of Administration Sub-Division of Land Management Office of BIFZA, Deputy Chairman 1 of the All-Indonesia Trade Union Confederation of Batam City, Expert Council Chairman of Local Youth Association of Batam City, Expert Council Chairman of Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Batam City, Vice Chairman of Batam Special All-Indonesia Housing and Settlement Developer Association, Chairperson of Commission 1 of Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, Head of Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City, public figures, community, and businessmen. While, the secondary data sources is several documents related.

Data is collected by interview [15 p362] and documentation study [15 p80]. The interview is collecting data by asking questions directly by researcher to informants in Batam. The informant's answers were recorded with a recording device. Meanwhile, documentation study is using documents that have been written from 2016 to understand the phenomena of research. Data was collected for next it is analyzed by process of reduction, presentation, and verification [15 p11]. Reduction is the process of selecting raw data obtained from interview recordings, written records, and other documents when on location. Presentation is the activity of presenting research data in form of processed narrative texts, tables and drawings, and verification is the activity of formulating conclusions based on the two previous activities.

4. Result and Discussion

4. 1. Reason of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change

Amount of annual mandatory money tariff is full authority by Head of Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA) with Finance Minister approval which based at Article 59 Government Regulation Number 40 of 1996. It Guideline is regulated at Article 3 Finance Minister Regulation Number 100/PMK.05/2016. Reason of annual mandatory money tariff change that is delivered by BIFZA is *first*, finance minister regulation. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by Finance Minister Regulation Number 148/PMK.05/2016 which replaces Finance Minister Regulation Number 153/PMK. 05/2012. It affects annual mandatory money tariff change that based at BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016 as a derivative regulation. This regulation is a policy in order to implement provisions of Article 28 and Article 29 of the Finance Minister Regulation Number 148/PMK.05/2016. BIFZA implements it because Ministry of Finance institutionally has a higher hierarchy in terms of related authority to regulate amount of annual mandatory money tariff.

Second, timeframe consideration. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by timeframe consideration between old and new annual mandatory money tariff that has not changed for a long time. It has not changed for 16 years. So, according to BIFZA, the long-unchanged policy is irrelevant and it needs to update according to economic condition in Batam at that time. The relevant of annual mandatory money tariff change according to BIFZA is broadly shown by percentage increase in tariff that is housing by 151,7% to 1.787% range, commercial by 176,1% to 868,1% range, industrial by 183,1% to 1.062,4% range, tourism by 195% to 395,2% range, cultivation area and others by 617,3% to 840,5% range, and public facilities and others by 470% to 2.640,4% range.

Third, Tax Object Selling Value adjustment. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 adjustment which is regulated by Batam City Government through Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City. Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 refers to Batam City Regulation Number 10 of 2011. Between the old annual mandatory money tariff and Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 show a high gap that is range of 1:2,5 to 1:33,2 comparisons to all subdistricts in Batam.

4. 2. Advantage and Disadvantage of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change

Phenomenon of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change in 2016 shows stakeholders who have competence in accordance with their interests about advantage and disadvantage which are obtained. Preference of each stakeholders was obtained from three choices that are between supporting, rejecting, or abstaining to respond it. And, description of political market was obtained in that is exchange aspect (*catallactics*) between supplier and demanders based on economical human aspect (*homo economicus*). Advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change based on preference and political market of stakeholders that are *first*, Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). It is competent as the authority to determine annual mandatory money tariff. BIFZA has been preference to supporting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are rejecting or abstaining. In political market, supporting to be a *catallactics* from BIFZA as a supplier to all demander which is based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 benefits all components of community in Batam by development effect, and no one sides is harmed.

Second, Community Organizations in Batam. It is competent as a presentation of interests from community and workers in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Community organizations in Batam have been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from community organizations in Batam as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms community and workers in Batam, and it actually benefits BIFZA.

Third, Businessman Organizations in Batam. It is competent as a presentation of interests from businessmen in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Businessman organizations in Batam have been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from businessman organizations in Batam as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms businessmen and community in Batam, and it actually benefits BIFZA.

Fourth, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City. It is competent as a aspirations receiver from all of community in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Regional House of Representatives of Batam City has been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from Regional House of

Representatives of Batam City as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms community in Batam, and it actually benefits Singapore and Malaysia.

Fifth, Batam City Government. It through Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City is competent as the authority to determine Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 that is one of the main reason of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Batam City Government has been preference to abstaining which related to annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or rejecting. In political market, Batam City Government gives a solution that is Special Economic Zone to the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Special Economic Zone provides new arrangement of distribution of land allocation services (specifically housing) between Batam City Government and BIFZA. This solution to be a *catallactics* from Batam City Government as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It is abstaining (not to determine) because they are a fellow executive institution that is not supposed to conflict.

5. Closing

5.1. Conclusion

The conclusions of this research are:

- a. Three reasons of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 are unilateral action from Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA) as a Public Service Agency because it does not coordinate with community organizations in Batam, businessman organizations in Batam, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, and Batam City Government which related to analysis of people purchasing power and economic conditions in Batam that based at Finance Minister Regulation Number 100/PMK.05/2016. Addition, in Tax Object Selling Value adjustment, coordination with Batam City Government was not carried out. Thus, the policy of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 caused controversy that is rejection from various sides, and it also disrupts economic activities in Batam because the determination was not included with clear guidelines.
- b. The advantage side of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is BIFZA because it is the highest income (it recorded 400 billion (*rupiah*) revenue from all of total 986 billion (*rupiah*) revenue in 2015 [16]), and also foreign investors because annual mandatory money is not a burden for them but a burden for domestic investors so that the it does not contribute to reducing the gap between them (difference in investment value in Batam in 2016 is US \$ 392,19 million for foreign investment and 20,17 million US \$ for domestic investment [9 p55]). While, the disadvantage sides of annual mandatory money change in 2016 are community, businessmen, and workers because of limited purchasing power to people, high investment expense to businessmen, and triggered employment termination to workers.

5.2. Recommendation

The recommendations to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority are:

- a. Does not determine annual mandatory money tariff change unilaterally but by coordinating to ask for input that related to people purchasing power, Tax Object Selling Value adjustment, amount of tariff determination, economic conditions and others to community organizations in Batam, Businessman organizations in Batam, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, and Batam City Government.
- b. Transparency related to all annual mandatory money tariff drafting processes that all sides can give input which based on their respective interests. So, a win-win solution can be achieved that is mutually benefit and not harm both sides.

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